

Agency Crisis, and Enterprise Financial Performance among listed Companies in the Nigerian Exchange Group

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ABSTRACT

The study examines vertical agency crises, corporate governance and enterprise performance among listed companies in the Nigerian Exchange Group. The study used longitudinal research design; secondary data was sourced from the audited annual statement of thirty six (36) non-financial companies during the period 2015 to 2021. Using the panel estimation technique, random estimation result showed that vertical agency crises appears to have a negative impact (0.125) which is statistically significant ($p=0.042$) at 5% level. Board independence appeared to have a negative impact (0.004) though not significant at 5% ($p=0.902$). Board size appeared to have a positive impact (0.005) and it is statistically significant at 5% ($p=0.013$). Considering the change in profit by 55.4% as a result of vertical agency crises, board independence and board size, the study concludes

these explanatory variables are drivers of financial performance of firms in the insurance sector. The study recommends as follows: (i) firms should take measures to align managers' interest with shareholders interest in order to forestall agency crises that could erode financial performance. One way of ensuing convergence of interest is through managers equity ownership; (ii) notwithstanding the insignificant impact board independence has on financial performance, corporate entities should continue to ensure their board of directors has more of non-executive directors. Also, corporate entities should ensure that non-executive members appointed to the board has the needed expertise to function in such capacity rather than being a rubber stamp member; and (iii) the size of the board should be in conformity to the provision of the code that the relative scale of operation and complexities of the corporate entities should be taking into consideration.

1. Introduction

The separation of ownership and control in companies has continued to draw the attention of researchers throughout the world due to several corporate scandals such as Enron, Health South Corporation, WorldCom, Tyco, and Lehman Brothers etc. (Bhagat & Bolton, 2013). These scandals had led to reforms across the globe such as the SarsBane Oxley Act of 2002 in the United States. In Nigeria, we had several corporate reforms such as the Corporate Governance (CG) code of 2003, 2007, 2011, 2014 and the recent being the Nigerian Code of CG issued by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria ([FRCN], 2018). The principal motive of CG is to control the opportunistic behavior of top level administrators and executives often found involved in corporate scams (Sabbaghi, 2016). The implementation of good CG mechanisms is expected to lead firms to accomplish better financial outcomes. The link between CG mechanisms and financial performance has been empirically investigated by many scholarships these studies did not arrived at a consensus (Kijkasiwat et al., 2022, Shafi et al., 2020, Ali et al., 2020). Other than the debate on whether or not prior result provides consensus findings, an area of concern is how vertical agency crises will impact financial performance. In the first instance, the call for CG is to checkmate the differing principal agent interest, which crystallizes to agency cost, a consequence of agency problem and a charge on financial performance.

Nguyen et al. (2020) opines that the agency problem could be classified into agency problem type 1, otherwise known as vertical agency crises and agency problem type 2, otherwise known as horizontal agency crises. The agency problem type 1 refers to the shareholder and management conflicts, which is the most common while agency problem type 2 refers to the problems between controlling shareholders and minority shareholders. The consequence of the disagreement is termed agency cost. Agency cost is a type of

internal company expense, which comes from the actions of an agent acting on behalf of a principal. Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Jensen (1986) described three kinds of agency costs as monitoring costs; bonding costs and residual loss. Studies on CG had not given much attention to vertical agency problem impacting financial performance, only a handful of studies exist (Premananda et al., 2022). However, the study of Premananda et al (2022) examined the factors that could possibly affect vertical agency crises such as board size, women participation on the board, proportion of non-executive directors etc. Vertical agency crises problem creates conflict in decision-making between managers and shareholders, consequently leading former who always focuses on his benefit by making excessive money, earning bonuses and secret cash in the way of unproductive business investment.

The implication of agency cost on the performance of firm is an inverse impact. Therefore, corporate entities must make concerted effort to address such issues. It is due to this conflict that board of directors (BoDs) is often appointed to oversee management activities. According to the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2018), a successful company is headed by an effective BoDs which is responsible for providing entrepreneurial and strategic leadership as well as promoting ethical culture and responsible citizens. As a link between stakeholders and the company, the BoDs is to exercise oversight and control to ensure that management acts in the best interest of shareholders and other stakeholders while sustaining the prosperity of the company. Thus, the BoDs acts as a CG mechanism to alleviate agency problems and to align principal and agent interests, and they also consider the interests of all stakeholders influenced by managers' decisions when performing their monitoring function (Jain & Jamali, 2016). With the responsibility of monitoring the management team, the BoDs plays a vital role for enhancing corporate performance. Bear et al. (2010) states that there is a need for an appropriate mixture of experience and capabilities from the BoDs in order to monitor the management team, and assess the business strategies and their influences. This suggests that some attributes of the BoDs may support and enhance corporate entities performance. Therefore, there is the need to examine how agency crises, as well as BoDs mix impact financial performance of corporate entities listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).

The study is structured as follows: section two is on literature review, section three is on methodology, section four is on results and discussion while section five presents the conclusion and recommendation.

2. Financial Performance

The concept of firm performance refers to how the financial goals of a company are being achieved using several measurements and performance indicators. Firm performance can also be defined as the ability of a firm to use its resources effectively and efficiently in such a way to achieve its objective (Al-Quad, 2017). Firm performance shows the overall health of a firm and allows for comparisons across sector, industry and at company level for business lines comparison. According to Ravichandran and Subramanian (2016), it is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. It measures the quantity, robustness and sturdiness of a firm's revenue generation growth. Ricci and Civitillo (2018) see it as the measurement of the level of achievement of a firm's economic and financial objectives periodically. Thus, financial performance, as a business concept, is a dynamic analytic tool employed by business firms to measure the progressive revenue growth, productivity and marginal rate of returns generated by the organization for the creation of long-term value (Gulati et al., 2016).

Firm financial performance has been operationalized in several ways such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), return on capital employed (ROCE) etc. Ameer and Mhiri (2013) see ROA as the ratio of net profit to total assets and it measures the ability of management to generate income by utilizing company assets at their disposal. In other words, it shows how efficiently the resources of the company are used to generate income. It is important to note that many factors can influence ROA such as firm's degree of capitalization. ROA favours highly capitalized institutions because it treats equity capital as free funds, i.e. there is no cost associated with them. According to Ameer and Mhiri (2013), ROE is the ratio of net profit to total equity; it represents the rate of return earned on the funds invested in the bank by its stockholders. It reflects how effectively a management is using shareholders' fund; it is what the shareholders look in return for their investment. A business that has a high return on equity is more likely to be one that is capable of generating cash internally. However, it should be noted that ROE is not flawless. Investors need to be aware that a disproportionate amount of debt in a company's capital structure would translate into a smaller equity base. Thus, a small amount of PAT could still produce a high ROE off a modest equity base.

Finally, the concept of financial performance connotes that a company must plan and achieve short, medium and long-term goals with a proficient use of its long-term assets and capital resources that are invested or deployed in the business (Sachs et al., 2019). Capital employed performance of a firm entails that consistent return is regularly generated to the shareholders from the capital invested (Purnamasari, 2015). Camelia (2019) posits that

capital employed performance is used by investors to analyze the level of appreciation that the capital invested in the firm has gained periodically. Generating adequate and consistent profits from the capital employed in a firm is necessarily a pre-requisite for business continuity, sustainability and going concern. This is usually done using the analytical measurement of ROCE ratio (Barros et al., 2021). Hence, the ROCE ratio is computed to aid operational, tactical and strategically decision-making by corporate managers of the firm. ROCE is therefore a financial metric used to quantify a firm's performance in terms of efficiency or profitability generated from the deployment of investors' capital. This study adopts the ROCE as a measure of financial performance. The reason being that it provides an indication that shows the level of returns generated by the capital provided by the both the equity holders and debt providers periodically.

Financial performance can be affected by several factors among which is the principal agent crises which lead to agency costs. Agency costs are the cost of a company due to self-centric behaviors by an agent of an organization who always focuses on his benefit by making excessive money, earning bonuses and secret cash in the way of unproductive business investment. Past literature suggests that the agent of a firm may not consistently act in line with the objectives of the principal, but on the other hand, the principal works for the whole objective of the concern. So, these types of conflict lead to an emergence of a problem inside the working environment of the firm, consequently, leads to zero value creation for the company. Nguyen et al. (2020) opines that the agency problem could be classified into agency problem type 1, otherwise known as vertical agency crises and agency problem type 2, otherwise known as horizontal agency crises. The agency problem type 1 refers to the shareholder and management conflicts, which is the most common while agency problem type 2 refers to the problems between controlling shareholders and minority shareholders. Therefore, agency crises, whether type 1 or type 2 creates conflict in decision-making, consequently leading to the overall failure of the firm.

The performance of a firm is very much essential for survival, growth and diversification in this competitive market. The collapse in the performance of a company leads to the emergence of several problems like labour turnover, stakeholder dissatisfaction and liquidation. Performance of the firm depends upon various factors such firm specific attributes, CG mechanisms such as board meetings (Chou et al., 2013; Buchdadi, 2019; Eluyela et al., 2018; Al-Daoud et al., 2016), board independence (Jaidiet al., 2021), woman director on the board (Jyothi & Mangalagiri, 2019), board size (Shunu, 2017) and presence of independent non-executive director on the board (Alhaji et al., 2013). However, giving that agency crises creates conflict in decision-making, this may adversely affect the

survival of a corporate entity. There seems to be no studies on the relationship between agency crises and performance, the study of seeks to contribute to knowledge in this regard. The study proposed that: (H₁) *that vertical integration crises has not significant impact on financial performance among listed firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group.*

Board independence refers to the ratio of independent outside directors to the total number of directors on the board. Outside directors are non-executive directors of either affiliate or independent in nature (Daily et al., 1999). The affiliate directors are those who have business ties with the firm, and this tends to undermine objective participation in board decision making. The independent directors are those directors who do not have direct or indirect relationship with the firm or its affiliate, therefore can objectively participate in the board. For board independence to be entrenched, the NCCG (2018) states that there should be an appropriate mix between the executive, non-executive and independent non-executive directors on the board. Preferably, that most of the non-executive directors should be independent. The executive directors support the Managing Director/Chief Executive Officer in the operations and management of the company. Non-executive directors bring to bear their knowledge, expertise and independent judgment on issues of strategy and performance on the board. Independent non-executive directors bring a high degree of objectivity to the board for sustaining stakeholder trust and confidence. The board of directors can reduce agency conflicts by exercising its power to monitor and control management (Fama & Jensen, 1983). Independent outside directors are presumed to carry out the monitoring function on behalf of shareholders to ensure that management is in place and to maximize shareholders' interests because shareholders themselves would find it difficult to exercise control due to the wide dispersion of ownership of common stock (John & Senbet, 1998). Similarly, Kesner and Dalton (1986) found that outside director is more independent since close relationship often do not exist with management. As a result, outside directors perform a better control and monitoring functions. Therefore, board independence is expected to improve organisation outcome such as financial performance.

Gordini (2012) examined the effect of outsiders on firm performance measured by ROA and ROI for a sample of 950 Italian small family firms (SFFs) from 2007 to 2009. The study found a positive relationship and reports that the NEDs improved firm performance and added value to the firm through their contributions such as skills, experiences and their linkage to the external resources. Khan and Awan (2012) examined the relationship between board independence and firm performance. Financial performance was measured using ROA, ROE and Tobin's Q and found a positive significant relationship

between the outside directors and the firm performance. . The study conclude that the greater the percentage of outsiders in the board will result in better firm performance and add value to the firm. This is because of the close monitoring and their valuable advices and contribution to the company. These findings are consistent with the view of agency and resource dependence theories. Conversely, Agrawal and Knoeber (1996), Bozec (2005) and Yermack (1996) provided evidence of a negative relationship between the NEDs and some performance measures. The third stream of this relationship provides evidence for no relationship between NEDs and firm performance (e.g. Arosa et al., 2012; Baysinger and Hoskinsson, 1990; Hermalin and Weisbach, 1991; Kumar and Singh, 2012). Thus, from an agency perspective, the NEDs are essential for the monitoring function as a safeguard for the shareholders' interests to monitor the manager's behaviours to reduce the agency problems to improve firm performance. This notion was supported also from the resource dependence theory view; NEDs provide the board with external experience, skills, knowledge and linkages to external network relationship. This will compensate for the skills of the internal directors and contribute with more ideas and knowledge. This might help in reducing the agency problem and affect the performance positively. As a result, if the NEDs perform their monitoring tasks and duties effectively, the likelihood of preventing management from expropriating the firm assets will be increased. This underlines the appropriateness of NEDs as a trustworthy regulatory mechanism in boards to ensure that managers function to maximise shareholders' wealth. The study proposed that: (H₂) *that board independence has not significant impact on financial performance among firms listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group.*

Board size refers to the number of directors on the board. Board size seems to differ from one country to another. This has led to two schools of thought: small; and large board size. The Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG, 2018) did not give a specific number of directors on the board. It states that the board should be of sufficient size to effectively undertake and fulfil its business; to oversee, monitor, direct and control the company's activities and be relative to the scale and complexity of its operation. It also states that the board should consider the following factors in determining the requisite number of its members are: (i) appropriate mix of knowledge, skills and experience, including the business, commercial and industry experience needed to govern the company; (ii) appropriate mix of executive, non-executive and independent non-executive members such that majority of the board are non-executive directors. It is desirable that most of the non-executive directors are independent; (iii) need for a sufficient number of members that qualify to serve on the committees of the board; (iv) need to secure quorum at meeting; and (v) diversity targets relating to the composition of the board. Prior researchers argued that

large board of director is more diversified in terms of directors' background, expertise and resources (Haniffa & Hudaib, 2006). In the same vein, large board of directors is more effective in monitoring, protecting shareholders interest and developing external linkages (Adams & Mehran, 2003; Harris & Raviv, 2008; Dalton et al., 1999). On small board size, Hermalin and Weisbach (2001) stated that a smaller board size offers a better monitoring on management. Prior studies have suggested that a company's performance is better when the board size is smaller (Andres et al. 2005). The reason is that decision making process is more effective, i.e. there is prompt and precise decision making (Yermack, 1996). However, the bane of small board size is that there could be absence of diversity such as expertise, nationality, external linkages etc. which could undermine firm output.

Yermack (1996) examined the relationship between board size and firm performance among 452 large US public firms during the period 1984 to 1991. Financial performance was measured using Tobin's Q and they found a negative relationship between the board size and firm performance. The study found that a small board has more favourable values for financial ratio. Also, Yermack (1996) They conclude that small boards are more productive than large ones, evidenced by decreased efficiency when board size increases, which is attributed to barriers in coordination and processes (Guest, 2008; Haniffa and Hudaib, 2006). However, Eisenberg et al., (1998) argued that Yermack's (1996) sample concentrating on large firms means that his findings cannot be transposed to smaller firms, which vary according to differences in the cultural environment. Eisenberg et al., 1998) studied 879 small- and medium-sized Finnish companies for the period 1992 to 1994, and found a negative relationship between the board size and the firm profitability measured by return on assets (ROA). In accordance with Yermack (1996), different studies (Bozec, 2005; Cheng et al., 2008) confirmed that small boards are more likely to be associated with lower agency costs leading to better performance. In contrast, other researchers reported that increased board size impacts the firm performance positively. Larmou and Vafeas (2010); Sheikh et al. (2012) found that when the board size increases, the market responds favourably. In their study they report that large boards provide better monitoring for companies with poor operating performance due to their diversity of backgrounds and communications skills. Sanda et al., (2005) studying a sample of 93 Nigerian listed firms during the period 1996 to 1999, found a positive correlation between the board size and the firm profitability as measured by return on equity (ROE). Their results support that large boards have better access than smaller ones to the external environment by offering better chances to have wide resource for finance and raw materials. This is in line with resource dependence theory that large boards offer greater access to their firm external environment, which facilitate and secure critical resources (e.g. raw materials and finance)

and reduces uncertainties (Pearce & Zahra, 1991). The later result is consistent with Kiel and Nicholson (2003), Beiner et al., (2006) and Coles et al., (2008). Haniffa and Hudaib (2006) found that the wider knowledge base inherent in larger boards facilitates better business decisions to reduce the agency problem. Mangena and Tauringana (2007) also found a positive relationship between the board size and the firm performance of 72 Zimbabwean listed firms for the period 2002 to 2004. They demonstrated that their results stayed fixed and unchanged even if using inflation adjusted data. This indicates that large boards provide important role of effective monitoring in uncertain economic and political periods to reduce agency problems and improve firm performance. The study proposed that: (H₃) *that board size has not significant impact on financial performance among listed firms the Nigerian Exchange Group.*

2.1 Theoretical Review

The study is anchored on the agency theory. The agency theory seeks to analyze the contractual relationship that exists between company owners (shareholders), and its agents (management). Although the separation of ownership from control presents some advantages such as the ability of ownership to change without impacting operation, the possibility of hiring expert to act as manager, however, it presents a much bigger challenge of wealth shifting from owners to agents. Apart from conflicting interest between owners and agents, there could also be conflicting interest between majority and minority shareholders. Agency theory explains the relationship between principals such as shareholders and agents such as a company's executives. In this relationship, the principal being the owners of the company, delegate or hires an agent (executive) to perform a work, in this case, to efficiently and effectively manage the investment of shareholders for a return (improving the owners wealth). This wealth could be measured using several parameters such as return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE) etc. In agency theory, it is expected that the agents (managers) protect the interest of its owners. In order to alleviate the negative consequences of this problem, agency theory describes the need for monitoring and contracting arrangements (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Agency theory predicts that, contracts such as compensation and reward schemes are used to keep the interests of owners and managers aligned. From these insights, company performance is predicted to be a function of the effectiveness of organizational specific contractual mechanisms for attracting, retaining and controlling managerial talent, in ways that maximize owners' wealth.

3. Methodology

The study used a longitudinal research design. The longitudinal design involves repeated observations of the same variables over long periods of time and the cross-sectional design which examines variables at a point in time. The population of the study consists of the entire one hundred and twelve (112) non-financial companies listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2021. The choice of the sector is due to the strict regulation in financial sector, making vertical agency crises less rampant compared to non-financial companies. The time frame for the study is a seven year period, 2015 to 2021. The sample size is fifty two (52) non-financial companies determined using the Yamane (1967) sampling size determination technique. However, the researcher reduces the sample size to thirty six (36) companies due to data cost, drawn from the population using simple random sampling technique. Secondary data was used for this study. The data were retrieved from the audited annual reports of insurance companies for 2015-2021 financial years. The researcher utilizes only audited annual reports because they are readily available, accessible and so provides a greater potential for comparability of results.

The study adopts the panel least square estimation technique. The choice of the panel least square technique is that it takes into consideration the problem of heterogeneity associated in a cross section study. In estimating the panel regression, the random effect was first conducted; there after the fixed effect is done if found that the result is undermined. The choice between the random and fixed effect is based on the outcome of the hausman test statistic. If the hausman test is less than 0.05, then it is significant and implies that the result cannot be used for valid policy implication. This leads us to conduct the estimation based on mean-corrected value, i.e. fixed effect estimation. Other post diagnostic tests such heteroschedasticity, serial correlation, model specification were carried out.

3.1 Model Specification

The study is anchored on the agency theory. The economic form of the model is given below:

$$FP_{it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 VAC_{it} + \beta_3 BN_{it} + \beta_4 BS_{it} + w_{it} \dots \dots \dots i$$

Where FP= financial performance, VAC= vertical agency crises, BN = board independence, BS = board size, β_1 = intercept for the thirty six (36) non-financial companies; $\beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = Unknown coefficients; i= Companies (1...36 companies); t= Time [(1...7 years), w_{it} = error term.

3.2 Measurement of Variables

Table 1: Variable measurement

Variables	Measurement	Justification	Apriori expectation
Firm profitability	The study used return on capital employed (ROCE) measured as the ratio of profit after tax to capital employed (asset plus debt)	Sabo (2018)	Nil
Vertical agency crises	Asset turnover ratio	Nguyen et al. (2020),	-
Board independence	Percentage of independent non executive directors to the total number of directors on the board	Kuan et al. (2011)	+
Board size	Number of directors on the board	Kuan et al. (2011)	+

Source: Researcher’s computation (2022)

4 Presentation and Discussion of results

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	J-Bera.	Probability	Obs.
/ROCE2	0.022	0.163	-0.221	0.057	159.491	0.000	252
VAC	0.105	0.575	0.025	0.058	282	0.000	252
BND	0.643	1.125	0.000	0.127	230	0.000	252

Source: Researchers Compilation (2022) from E-View 9

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for the variables and as observed, the mean ROCE stood at 0.022, which suggests the average returns in form of profit after tax on capital employed is about 2.2 % level, with the highest and lowest observation scores of 0.163 and -0.221 respectively. The standard deviation stood at 0.058 which indicates clustering around the mean. The mean VAC stood at 0.105, which suggests that the average asset utilization is about 10.5%, with the highest and lowest observation scores of 0.575 and 0.025 respectively. The standard deviation stood at 0.058 which indicates clustering around the mean. The mean BND stood at 0.643, which suggests that the average board ration of independent directors to total directors is about 64.3%, with the highest and lowest

observation scores of 1.125 and 0.000 respectively. The standard deviation stood at 0.127 which indicates considerable level of dispersion from the mean. The mean BS stood at 9.599, which suggests that the average board size for the sample firm is about 9 members, with the highest and lowest observation scores of 18.000 and 4.000 respectively. The standard deviation stood at 3.150 which indicates clustering around the mean. Jacque-Bera probability values were all significant ($p = 0.000$) at 1%, which indicates the presence of outliers in the distribution. However, this does not give a cause for concern.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Result

	ROCE	VAC	BND	BS
ROCE	1			
VAC	-0.105* (0.094)	1		
BND	-0.007 (0.908)	0.032 (0.618)	1	
BS	0.128** (0.042)	0.008 (0.897)	0.015 (0.810)	1

Source: Researchers Compilation (2022) from E-View 9

Table 3 shows the correlation relationship between the firm financial performance (ROCE as measures) which is the dependent and the explanatory variables. The correlation statistics gives an indication of the direction and magnitude of relationships between the variables. Positive correlations indicate that increase in one variable is associated with increases in the other and vice-versa. The results reveal that ROCE is positively correlates with BS ($r= 0.128$), BGD ($r=0.026$) and INSOWN ($r= 0.066$) while it negatively correlates with VAC ($r= -0.105$), BND ($r= -0.007$) and AT ($r=-0.068$). Only VAC and BS exhibit significant relationship with, however the strength of the relationship differs.

4.1 Panel Regressions

Table 4: Regression Result

	Aprori sign	Dependent Variable: ROCE		
		Random effects Estimates	Fixed effects estimates	POOL
C		0.040 (0.043) {0.358}	0.036 (0.175) {0.834}	0.033 (0.032) {0.299}
VAC	-	-0.125** (0.061) {0.042}	-0.136** (0.065) {0.037}	-0.105* (0.063) {0.094}
BND	+	-0.004 (0.030) {0.902}	0.007 (0.035) {0.853}	-0.008 (0.029) {0.792}
BS	+	0.005** (0.001) {0.013}	0.007** (0.002) {0.005}	0.003** (0.002) {0.039}
Model Parameters				
R ²		0.554	0.321	0.440
Adjusted R ²		0.527	0.185	0.412
F-statistic		1.976*	2.354***	1.453
Prob(F-stat)		0.059	0.000	0.184

Durbin-Watson		1.6	1.9	1.3
Huassman Test	3.21, p = 0.864			

Source: Researcher's compilation (2022) from E-views 9. * sig @10%, ** sig @ 5% *** sig @ 1% () Standard error{ } p-values

Table 4 shows the regression result using ROCE measure of performance. From the result, the random effect estimation is preferred to the fixed effect estimation as revealed by the hausman test result of p-value = 0.864. The random estimation result showed R^2 is 0.554 which suggests that the explanatory variables explains about 55.4% of systematic variations in financial performance with an adjusted value of 0.527. The F-stat (1.976) and p-value (0.059) indicates that the hypothesis of a significant linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables cannot be rejected at 10% level while the D.W statistics of 1.6 indicates that the presence of serial correlation in the residuals is unlikely. Commenting on the performance of the specific explanatory variables, we observe that VAC appears to have a negative impact (0.125) which is statistically significant ($p=0.042$) at 5% level. BND appeared to have a negative impact (0.004) though not significant at 5% ($p=0.902$). BS appeared to have a positive impact (0.005) and it is statistically significant at 5% ($p=0.013$).

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The discussion of the result is based on the random effects estimation in table 4. The results are discussed below;

4.2.1 Vertical integration crises and financial performance

The results show that we observe that VAC, as measure using the asset utilization ratio appears to have a negative impact (0.125) which is statistically significant ($p=0.042$) at 5% level. This suggests that increase in the asset utilization ratio by a unit would lead to a fall in profit by 12.5%, and it is significant. Based on the statistically significant criteria, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) that vertical integration crises has not significant impact on financial performance among listed firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group. Vertical integration crises being negatively signed conforms to a priori and theoretical expectation. The descriptive statistics shows asset utilization of the sampled firms by 10.5%, this suggests that about 89.5% of assets is idle and that managerial efficiency is low. The unutilized ratio could

entrenched agency cost in the sense that managers could divert the assets for their private gain, consequently adversely affecting profit.

4.2.2 Board independence and financial performance

The results show that we observe that BND appeared to have a negative impact (0.004) though not significant at 5% ($p=0.902$). This suggests that increase in board independence by one unit would lead to a decline in profit, although it is insignificant. Based on the statistically insignificant criteria, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_2) *that board independence has not significant impact on financial performance among firms listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group*. Board independence being positively signed does not conform to a priori and theoretical expectation. The result is in tandem with the study of Duchin et al. (2010) who showed that external directors may be beneficial, but if the cost outweighs the benefits, their presence may decrease firm performance. In their study, a sample was collected from U.S firms to ascertain how much board independence affects performance. They did not find any indication that if board independence is increased, this will lead to improved firm performance. These authors suggest that internal directors are more able to understand the operation of the company; they know everything about the company, and they have expertise. Although they argue that they add more value than outside directors, an ideal board is one having both executive and non-executive directors. Also, Agrawal and Knoeber (1996), Bozec (2005) and Yermack (1996) provided evidence of a negative relationship between the NEDs and some performance measures.

4.2.3 Board size and financial performance

The results show that we observe that BS appeared to have a positive impact (0.005) and it is statistically significant at 5% ($p=0.013$). This suggests that increase in the size of the board by a member would lead to a rise in profit by 0.005 units and it is significant. Based on the statistically significant criteria, we reject the null hypothesis (H_3) *that board size has not significant impact on financial performance among listed firms the Nigerian Exchange Group*. Board size being positively signed in conforms to a priori and theoretical expectation. The result is in tandem with the study of Larmou and Vafeas (2010); Sheikh et al. (2012) found that when the board size increases the market responds favourably. In their study they report that large boards provide better monitoring for companies with poor operating performance due to their diversity of backgrounds and communications skills. Sanda et al., (2005) studying a sample of 93 Nigerian listed firms during the period 1996 to 1999, found a positive correlation between the board size and the firm profitability as measured by return on equity (ROE). Their results support that large boards have better access than smaller ones to the external environment by offering better chances to have wide resource for

finance and raw materials. This is in line with resource dependence theory that large boards offer greater access to their firm external environment, which facilitate and secure critical resources (e.g. raw materials and finance) and reduces uncertainties (Pearce and Zahra, 1991). Haniffa and Hudaib (2006) found a positive relationship between the board size and the firm performance as measured by ROA, which is in contrast with their prior finding of a negative relationship between board size and the firm performance measured by Tobin's Q. The later result is consistent with Kiel and Nicholson (2003), Beiner et al., (2006) and Coles et al., (2008).

5. Conclusion and recommendations

The principal motive of corporate governance is to control the opportunistic behavior of top level administrators and executives often found involved in corporate scams. The implementation of good CG mechanisms is expected to lead firms to accomplish better financial outcomes. The link between CG mechanisms and corporate financial performance has been empirically investigated by many scholarships. Other than the debate on whether or not prior result provides consensus findings, an area of concern is how vertical agency crises will impact financial performance. In the first instance, the call for corporate governance is to checkmate the differing principal agent interest, which crystallizes to agency cost, a charge on financial performance. It is due to this conflict that board of directors is often appointed to oversee management activities. Therefore, studies on corporate governance had not giving much attention to vertical agency problem impacting financial performance, only a handful of studies exist. Vertical agency crises problem creates conflict in decision-making between managers and shareholders, consequently leading former who always focuses on his benefit by making excessive money, earning bonuses and secret cash in the way of unproductive business investment. Therefore, then study examined how vertical agency crises, corporate governance factors affect financial performance of non-financial listed firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group. The study hypothesises that vertical integration crises, board independence, board size, board gender diversity and institutional ownership do not have significant impact on financial performance of non-financial companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Using the random effects estimation after conducting the relevant preliminary diagnostic test, the study revealed that vertical integration crises and board size have significant impact on financial performance at 5% while board independence, board gender diversity and institutional ownership do not significant impact financial performance. Considering the change in profit by 55.4% as a result of vertical integration crises and board independence, board size, board gender diversity and institutional ownership, the study concludes these explanatory variables are drivers of financial performance of firms in the

insurance sector. The study recommends as follows: (i) firms should take measures to align managers' interest with shareholders interest in order to forestall agency crises that could erode financial performance. One way of ensuing convergence of interest is through managers equity ownership; (ii) notwithstanding the insignificant impact board independence has on financial performance, corporate entities should continue to ensure their board of directors has more of non-executive directors. Also, corporate entities should ensure that non-executive members appointed to the board has the needed expertise to function in such capacity rather than being a rubber stamp member; and (iii) the size of the board should be in conformity to the provision of the code that the relative scale of operation and complexities of the corporate entities should be taking into consideration.

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